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Marital Income As A Predictor Of Marital Instability Among Married Teachers In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined marital income as a predictor of marital instability among married persons in Anambra State. Two research questions and Two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 5,147 married teachers in the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Sample consisted of 515 married teachers (81 males and 434 female teachers). The questionnaire was used for as the instrument of data collection. Simple linear regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that marital income significantly predicted marital instability among married teachers. Additionally, marital income significantly predicts marital instability among male and female teachers. The study concluded that marital income was a significant predictor of marital instability among married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State with significant differences in terms of gender. The study recommended that married teachers should be encouraged to participate in financial literacy and income management programs, as improved financial planning would reduce economic stressors and in turn, lessen the risk of marital instability.

Keywords: Marital Income, Marital Instability, Gender

INTRODUCTION

The marriage institution is as old as the creation of man. The union dates back to the era of Adam and Eve in the Holy Bible. It is the sacramental and conjugal coming together of two persons in love with parental consent, guardians and witnesses for the purpose of procreation and harmonious companionship. It is an essential phenomenon in human life irrespective of tribe, society and religious affiliations. In the opinion of Ahmadi (2025), marriage is a religious duty and is consequently a moral safeguard as well as a social necessity. It has been observed that marriage serves as a moral safeguard because it acts as an outlet for sexual needs and regulates man's sexual desire so that man does not become a slave to it. The assumption for its social necessity is rested on the premise that through it, families are established and the family is the fundamental unit of human society. Marriage is a social contract between two individuals to become husband and wife. Marriage as ordained by God gives legitimacy to sexual relationship and reproduction for legitimate children (Akumma, 2021). In the words of Igbokwe (2021), marriage is the state of being united with a person of the opposite sex as husband or wife for the purpose of companionship, procreation and maintaining a family. Marriage is a special contract of union between a man and woman in accordance with the law which establishes conjugal and family life. It is the foundation of family and inviolable social institutions whose nature, consequences and incident are governed by law and stipulation.

Marriage is a culturally approved relationship of one man and one woman (monogamy), one man and two or more women (polygyny), of one woman and two or more men (polyandry) in which there is cultural endorsement of sexual intercourse between the marital partners of opposite sex and with the expectation that children would be born of the relationship (Abubakar 2018). From a societal level of analysis, the institution of marriage represents all the behaviours, norms, roles, expectations, and values that are associated with the legal union of a man and woman. Marriage is considered to

represent a lifelong commitment by two people to each other, and it signified by a contract sanctioned by the state. It thus involves legal rights, responsibilities, and duties that are enforced by both secular and sacred laws. Marriage is expected to be an affair of intimacy and compromise, joint income generation and free hearty communication, where spouses complement each other. It is also expected to be a union of “for better, for worse”, but the recent happenings in the institution of marriage trend has departed from original and traditional assertions to becoming a mere association where rancour, conflict, savage mutual attacks, disparity, domestic violence and acrimony are endemic. Ali et al. (2022) concluded that unrealistic spousal role expectations, particularly around emotional intimacy, conflict resolution, joint responsibilities and supportive communication, significantly precipitate marital conflict and escalate into hostility and violence in intimate partnerships

The researcher viewed marriage as a legally recognized union between two people who willingly come together in a personal relationship to become one. It could be legally and socially sanctioned union, usually between a man and a woman, that is regulated by laws, rules, customs, beliefs, traditions and attitudes that prescribe the rights and duties of the partners and accords status to their offspring and fosters happiness in marriage. However, contemporary marriages seems to have witnessed a lots of chaos and misunderstanding resulting to marital instability.

Marital instability is always a human tragedy that is desired by no one. It causes hurt and suffering to human persons. It is an experience, which involves serious disruption of life at many levels. Many people who have been through the experience of a marital instability liken it to the experience of bereavement (Ifemeje, 2020). However, marital instability has become a thing of concern in this contemporary society and is the process whereby marriages breakdown through separation, divorce, and widowhood. Separation and divorce are social phenomena created by either husband or the wife or both, but widowhood is beyond the control of human being, it is related to death and thus universal (Amina, 2018). Meanwhile separation can be in two categories: physical separation that is, when the husband and wife reside separately without resolving their marital tie. It is imperative to note that when marriage is dissolved in the court of law, it is called divorce, but when it is dissolved by death is called widowhood (Amina, 2019). Unfortunately, many children today are faced with the challenges of multiple divorces or separations within their families. Parents who divorce often goes on to remarry or form other intimate relationships have higher incidence of failure (Amato, 2017).

Furthermore, marital instability has characterized the family scene in Anambra State. Thus, Ifemeje (2020) observed that increasing cases of marital instability besiege social welfare homes in Anambra State. She further stated that the statistical data collected from some various areas revealed that the social welfare unit handled over 827 cases of marital problems and 194 cases of matrimonial conflicts between the years 2018 and 2019. She went on to say that it is believed that this is an eye opener to the fact that there is actually an increase in the general rate of family breakdown in Anambra State but most couples avoid going to court for the dissolution of such unstable marriages, probably for the sake of the off springs of the marriage, the cultural background and social desirability fact which demand that women should be submissive to their husbands and families wanting to be seen as good or better than each other. In Anambra State, the involvement of women in wage earnings is a threat in the family solidarity; couples hardly find time to stay together for interaction purposes (Ojukwu & Obiji, 2016). Child care which should be the responsibility of the parents is now shifted to the school and house helps (Onoyase, 2017).

Marital instability refers to the interpersonal difficulties within the marital relationship (Akumma, 2021). It is defined also as ongoing conflict in marriage because of communication problems, disagreements about parenting or gender roles, financial difficulties, untrustworthiness, infidelity, or alcohol and drug abuse (Booth et al, 2019). Marital instability refers to the process where marriages breakdown through separation, desertion, or divorce (Lesmin & Sarah, 2018). Dessislav (2017) wrote thus: the family is the most basic unit of society and building block for national development. Just as there cannot exist any society without families or home, there cannot be sustainable development without stable families or home. In this study, marital instability is described as the interpersonal difficulties within the marital relationship.

There are also some social factors that affect the instability of the marriage. Marital conflict often arises early on in a marriage merely because one partner, or perhaps both, had unrealistic expectations about marriage before their wedding and suddenly finds himself living with someone he barely knows and has little in common with. Money issues are common cause of marital problems. Lack of

intimacy in marriage is important and also one of the most common causes of marital instability (Alireza & Bagher, 2021). Many causative factors such as incompatible needs of couples, poor communication skills, distorted beliefs, extreme emotional reactions and negative enforcing patterns can trigger instabilities in marriages. Also, splitting of chores, change in appearance, fertility struggles, poor communication, infidelity and inconsistency beliefs are some of the common factors responsible for marital instability (Akumma, 2021).

Also, the idea of managing more than one wife might lead to marital instability. The habits that either the wife or the husband is involved in extra marital affairs which are perpetuated by some men and some women might lead to an end of the family (Onoyase, 2017). Again, the habits that either the wife or the husband is addicted to smoking or drinking also lead to marital dissolution. Lack of trust in many families amongst the couples is wrecking marriages today. Peer influences also threaten the marital solidarity if care is not taken by couples. As a result of outside influences, irrational decisions are made to the detriment of one's wish and this might lead to a marital crisis (Asa & Nkan, 2018). Other factors such as demographic variables (such as age, gender, education etc), illegitimate children, religion and infertility of the wife also initiate instability in the marriage. Marital instability in this study could emanate from marital income.

Income is the money received, especially on a regular basis, for work or through investments. It may be derived from wages, salaries, rental income, interest, dividends, or returns on investments. Individuals receive regular income through employment or by investing in financial assets such as stocks, bonds, and real estate. Essentially, income is the flow of cash or its cash equivalents received from work (wages or salary), capital (interest or profit), and land (rent) (OECD, 2022). Marital income refers to the total financial earnings, shared assets, and economic resources that couples acquire or receive during the course of their marriage. It plays a significant role in determining the financial stability and independence of the union, especially for men, as it is often linked to household decision-making, economic security, and overall marital satisfaction (Cherlin & Seltzer, 2021). Marital income in marriage is a pre-requisite for marital stability especially for men as it determines the financial independence and stability in such union (Igbokwe, 2021). In marital relationship, couples may be confronted by consequences of their own fear, emotion, cultural practices, anxiety, perception, beliefs and actions. Marital income is all the assets and properties acquired by spouses during the course of their marriage (Anih, 2017). The assets and properties that an individual owns before a marriage is considered separate properties, but the inheritances or third-party gifts given to an individual during a marriage all comprise to marital income. No one can be said to be psychologically healthy when he is engulfed in fear and anxiety and lacks the ability to generate income to sustain its family which most often end up in a dismay in marriage (Usoroh et al., 2020). In modern society, especially in Igboland where westernization and enculturation are fast taking deep root in people's way of living, some person's social beliefs, values, ideas and practices are in contrast and pose a big threat to the survival of marriage especially in this money modern society where money is the ultimate factors in any relationship and marriages (Ojukwu & Obiji, 2016). This is more so, as people's beliefs, values, ideas and practices are moving away from the traditional to western oriented beliefs, values, ideas and practices.

Inadequate marital income might bring about marital instability in the family (Anih, 2017). He further argued that the marital instability as a result of low income has become one of the most prevalent and endemic social challenges ravaging many families and communities in Nigeria. Since the family is the bedrock on which every society is built, the question of achieving national stability must first be addressed from the family unit with special reference to conflicts in marriages as a result of family income. Marriage carries certain legal implications with respect to property, money, and debt. Most married persons fight, get separated or divorced over financial problems that results from the marital incomes. When there is a low earnings or income in the marriage, there is high tendency that marital conflicts will continue to occur which often times result to separation or divorce (Umar as cited in Ifemeje, 2020). Low income in marriage can be influenced by the demographic features of the people involved.

The demographic variable such as gender is a vital factor in determining marital instability among married persons. Gender is the characteristics that differentiate the masculinity from femininity. It is the societal meaning assigned to male and female. Gender in this study refers to the sex of individual either male or female. Gender in effect is determined by the conception of tasks, functions and roles

attributed to women and men in society and in public and private life. This is supported by Oboh et al. (2020) who reported that gender effect could be a factor in determining the individuals' participation in family decision-making in Anambra State. Allana et al. (2018) argued that gender is very relevant and extremely significant in a situation where women are being marginalized. Believes, social norms, behaviours, values, policies, mindsets, processes et cetera all close gross discrimination against women. Thus, gender of individuals are considered in this study as it is a vital components in understanding marital income and communication gap in existing marriages.

Understanding what causes marital instability remains a critical issue in Nigeria and Anambra State in particular. Many researchers agreed that there are numerous factors that can cause marital instability. However, not much known to the researcher has been done on the predictive value of marital income on marital instability in Anambra State. As observed by the researcher, there is high rate of divorce and separation, along with disputes in several families in Anambra State. As there are regular meetings and gathering of elders and community heads, trying to settle issues and problems that pertains to marriages. In this regard, the study deemed it necessary to examine marital income as a predictor of marital instability among married teachers in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predictive value of marital income on marital instability among married teachers in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of marital income on marital instability of male and female married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Marital income would not significantly predict marital instability among married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Marital income would not significantly predict marital instability among married male and female teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted a correlational research design. The researcher adopted this design because of its appropriateness for this study which is to determine the marital income as a predictor of marital instability in Anambra State. The study was carried out in Anambra State. The choice of the area for the study was informed by the high rate of marital instability in the State which may be attributed to marital income. The population of the study comprised 5,147 married teachers in the 267 public secondary schools in six Education Zones in Anambra State. The study used a total sample of 515 secondary school teachers from public schools across the six education zones in Anambra State. These teachers were selected using a combination of two sampling techniques: simple random sampling and proportionate stratified random sampling to ensure fair representation from all zones. First, simple random sampling by balloting was used to select 8 public secondary schools from each of the six Education Zones (Aguata, Awka, Nnewi, Ogidi, Onitsha, and Otuocha). The gender distribution of the total sample (515 teachers) consisted of 81 males and 434 females.

Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. The instrument is made up of two sections; A and B. Section A; sought demographic information of the respondents such as gender and income. The second was 'Marital Instability Questionnaire (MIQ)' developed by Booth et al (2013). The researcher adapted the instruments. The questionnaire contains 12-items which sought information on Marital Instability of teachers. The items were placed on a four point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The range of scores was weighed as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses one to four at 0.05 level of significance while multiple regressions was used to test hypothesis five at 0.05 level of significance. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, therefore, where the p -value obtained was below the 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected which implies that there was no significant relationship between the variables. However, where the p -value was greater the 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected which implies that there was no significant relationship between the variables. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was used.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Analyses of Research Questions

Research Question One: *What is the predictive value of marital income on marital instability among married teachers in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Predictive Value of Marital Income on Marital Instability among Married Teachers

	B	SE	β
Constant	30.998	0.399	
Marital Income	0.751	0.451	0.559
R	0.759		
R ²	0.576		
Adj.R ²	0.523		

Table 1 measured the predictive value of marital income on marital instability among married teachers in Anambra State. The table indicates that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.751 while the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.576 shows that 57.6 percent of the variations in marital instability are predicted by the variation in marital income. Using Muijs' criteria, the predictive value of marital income on marital instability among married teachers in Anambra State is significant. The beta weight (β = 0.159) is an indication that predictive value of marital income on marital instability is significant among married teachers in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the predictive value of marital income on marital instability of male and female married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Predictive Value of Marital Income on Marital Instability of Male and Female Married Teachers

		B	SE	β
Male	Constant	29.728	0.474	
	Marital Income	4.407	0.561	0.573
	R	0.773		
	R ²	0.598		
	Adj.R ²	0.501		
Female	Constant	31.443	0.615	
	Marital Income	3.506	0.451	0.517
	R	0.717		
	R ²	0.514		
	Adj.R ²	0.496		

Table 2 above analyzed the the predictive value of marital income on marital instability of male and female married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The table showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) for male and female married teachers is 4.407 and 3.506 respectively while the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.598 and 0.514 respectively. This is an indication that marital income predicts 59.8 percent of the variations in marital instability among married male teachers and 51.4 percent of the variations in marital instability among married female teachers. Using Muijs' criteria, marital income predicts marital instability of male and female married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The beta weight value of 0.573 and 0.517 respectively for married male and female teachers indicates that marital income positively predicts marital instability of male and female married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Marital income would not significantly predict marital instability among married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis Summary for Marital Income Predicting Marital Instability

	<i>B</i>	SE	β	P-value
Constant	30.998	0.399		0.000
Marital Income	0.751	0.451	0.559	0.001
R	0.759			
R ²	0.576			
Adj.R ²	0.523			
<i>F</i>	11.805			0.001

Table 3 tested the statistical significance of the predictive value of marital income on marital instability among married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The table indicated that the coefficient of the regression result (R) is 0.751 while the R² is 0.576. The F-ratio associated with these is 11.805 and the P-value = 0.001. Therefore, since P-value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, we reject the stated hypothesis. The study therefore concludes that marital income significantly predicts marital instability among married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: Marital income would not significantly predict marital instability among married male and female teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis Summary for Marital Income Predicting Marital Instability among Married Male and Female Teachers

	<i>B</i>	SE	β	<i>P-value</i>
Male	Constant	29.728	0.474	0.000
	Marital Income	4.407	0.561	0.573
	R	0.773		
	R ²	0.717		
	Adj.R ²	0.598		
	<i>F</i>	31.186		
Female	Constant	31.443	0.615	0.000
	Marital Income	3.506	0.561	0.517
	R	0.717		
	R ²	0.514		
	Adj.R ²	0.496		
	<i>F</i>	25.849		

Table 4 tested the statistical significance of the predictive value of marital income on marital instability among married male and female teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The table indicated that the simple regression coefficient (R) for married male and female teachers is 4.407 and 3.506 respectively while the R² is 0.598 and 0.717 respectively for married male and female teachers. The F-ratio associated with these is 31.186 and 25.849 respectively for married male and female teachers while the P-value is 0.000 and 0.000 for married male and female teachers respectively. Since the P-values are less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, hypothesis three is rejected. Therefore, marital income significantly predicts marital instability among married male and female teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study were discussed in line with the research questions and hypotheses raised in the study. The result of the study presented on Table 1 indicated that the predictive value of marital income on marital instability among married teachers in Anambra State is significant. The result of the null hypotheses revealed that marital income significantly predicted marital instability among

married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This showed that marital income influences marital instability among married teachers. The finding of the present study is in line with Igbokwe (2021) who found that income is a significant determinant of marital instability. Similarly, this agreed with the findings of Tolorunleke (2019) that finance is one of the major causes of marital conflicts amongst couples in Nigeria. In the same vein, Asa and Nkan (2018) found that economic/financial factors are the major factors associated with marital instability. However, the finding is contrary to that of Onoyase (2017) who found that income does not significantly contribute to marital instability, but rather emphasized that communication breakdown and emotional incompatibility were more critical predictors of marital problems.

The result of the study as shown in Table 2 indicated that marital income positively predicts marital instability of male and female married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The result of the null hypotheses revealed that marital income significantly predicts marital instability among married male and female teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implied that marital income influences marital instability among male and female married teachers. This agreed with the findings of Anih (2017), and Asa and Nkan (2018), who indicated that the low financial status of couples significantly contributed to marital instability. Baktash et al., (2023) also found in a German cohort that when wives receive performance-based pay, marital instability increases substantially, highlighting gender-specific income dynamics in marriage. Similarly, Cai and Li (2024) reported in their study of Chinese couples that disparities in relative income between spouses are strongly associated with marital dissatisfaction, especially among lower-earning partners. However, some scholars offered contrasting perspectives. Kapelle and colleagues (2021) discovered that the impact of wives' relative income on marital dissolution has significantly weakened over time in Germany; in more recent cohorts, higher female earnings did not predict greater divorce risk, and in some cases, were associated with lower risk.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated marital income as a predictor of marital instability among married teachers in Anambra State. The data generated were subjected to statistical analysis and the following became evidence. The study found that marital income significantly predicts marital instability among married teachers in public secondary schools. The study also found that marital income significantly predicts marital instability among married male and female teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the foregoing, the study concludes that marital income was a significant predictor of marital instability among married teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State with significant differences in terms of gender.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Married teachers should be encouraged to participate in financial literacy and income management programs, as improved financial planning would reduce economic stressors and in turn, lessen the risk of marital instability.
2. Gender-sensitive marital support services should be incorporated into teacher welfare initiatives to address the unique challenges faced by both male and female married teachers. Such tailored interventions were expected to enhance relationship satisfaction and stability across genders.
3. The Ministry of Education should partner with family life educators and psychological counsellors to implement comprehensive marital support programs focusing on both income-related issues. This integrated approach would help address the root causes of instability and promote overall teacher well-being.

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